

Quantum Nature of Gravity

to explain Dark Matter and Dark Energy

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Abstract

Although gravitation as described by Newton is an elementary force, gravity constant G is still the least precisely known in physics. In the 20th century observations on galaxy rotation showed significant violation of Newton's law, leading to ongoing search for Dark Matter (DM) versus modified Newton dynamics. In addition, at the end of the last century observation of accelerated expansion for the Universe raised the issue of missing Dark Energy (DE).

In this article I describe quantum nature of gravitation in deriving an Elementary Quantum Gravity Model (EQGM) for the Universe and do find agreement with astronomical observations. The model comprises fluctuations with quantum energy states and quantum exchange particles.

It provides a law for zero-point gravitational acceleration explaining observed galaxy rotation. Furthermore, quantum uncertainty proves to explain observed DE and DM effects, as well as observed accelerated expansion of the Universe in line with the Standard Model of Cosmology.

Based on the new model, discrete gravitational quantization effects between mass objects are proposed. Moreover, also energy contained in the Universe, a minimum size for it, as well as a limit for minimum mass and granularity of time in the Universe are discussed.

Finally I show that gravitation as such can be described out of quantum mechanical uncertainty based on inertia, hence also explaining the corresponding equivalence principle.

Key words: quantum cosmology, quantum gravity, dark matter, modified Newton dynamics, dark energy, equivalence principle

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1. Introduction

To date the gravitational force between two mass bodies is described by Newton's law [1] and was first confirmed in measurement by Henry Cavendish in the 18th century [2]:

$$F_g = \frac{m_1 * m_2 * G}{r^2} \quad \text{with} \quad G = 6.6743 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-2}.$$

Since then it has been tried to describe its nature, leading to general relativity theory of Albert Einstein in the 20th century, as a geometric approach on space-time [3]. Although discovered more than three centuries ago, G is still the most imprecisely determined constant in physics [4], with a relative uncertainty of $2.2 \cdot 10^{-5}$.

Moreover, despite intense and diverse attempts to link gravity and quantum mechanics over the last decades, leading to a two-digit number of competing approaches, none of them proves so far to qualitatively and quantitatively resolve major inconsistencies with gravitation observed in nature. Overviews reflecting the state of research can be found for example in [5], [6], [7].

With advancement in astronomical measurement techniques, it was found from observational statistics of galaxies, that their rotation does not follow the Newton law of gravitation in the outer regime, since forces calculated are too low to explain the higher observed rotational velocities [8].

To solve this issue, at least two directions of research are still followed: The search for DM, to cause an on top gravitational effect in Newton's law, versus a modified Newton dynamic, which so far is empirical guessing to fit to the observed behavior of galaxies [9].

Even worse, at the end of the 20th century astronomical observations led to the conclusion that expansion of the Universe as described by Edwin Hubble is even accelerating [10], contradicting the belief that gravitation slows down its inflation. This leads to search for a missing DE required, being multiples larger than gravitational energy attached to visible matter in the Universe, however which needs to be in line with observed Standard Model of Cosmology [11].

In this article I follow the approach, that any physical model and law should be as simple as possible, only as complicated as necessary, and in line with proven observations and physical models. Thus it should help to overcome the state quantum gravity research is stuck in, and gain new insights into the nature of gravitation.

2. Deriving an Elementary Quantum Gravity Model (EQGM)

Following the aim of this article, I use proven basic quantum mechanical laws and models to compose an Elementary Quantum Gravity Model (EQGM). This means developing an analogue

gravity model out of atom and solid state physics, practically following an approach as proposed for example in [12]. Its key results shall serve to understand astronomical observations and effects behind the required assumption of DM and DE.

2.1. Approach for quantization

To introduce quantum mechanics, I start with the Heisenberg uncertainty, which is written as momentum-location and energy-time uncertainty relations [13]. It is used in the one-dimensional form with $x = r$ to address a radially symmetric Universe, and adapted with the Lorentz factor γ to consider relativistic effects¹.

Hence, the variance of momentum and location, as well as of energy and time for a mass body all must have non-zero minimum values. With the reduced Planck quantum of action $\hbar = \frac{h}{2\pi}$ and

$$h = 6.62607015 \cdot 10^{-34} \text{ J it writes: } \sigma_p^* \sigma_x \geq \frac{\hbar}{2} \text{ and } \sigma_W^* \sigma_t \geq \frac{\hbar}{2} .$$

Now I apply the Heisenberg uncertainty to a mass body (mb) with mass m in the Universe (U). The radius of the Universe is the boarder confining the location of the body in a gravitational potential well, while the time uncertainty is related to the time in the Universe.

In the relativistic view of the energy of the body, in principle its uncertainty can be rooted in the kinetic energy or in the rest energy.

2.1.1. Kinetic energy uncertainty

For the first case, using the kinetic energy equivalent for the body from the gravitational potential, the uncertainties are set up as equations, anticipating minimum energy possible:

$$\sqrt{2^*} \sigma_{WU}(m) = -W_{pot}(m) = \int_{\infty}^{R_U} \frac{m^* M_U^* G}{r^2} dr = \frac{m^* M_U^* G}{R_U} = W_{kin}(m) \text{ and hence:}$$

$$\sqrt{2^*} \sigma_{tU} = \frac{2^* R_U^* \hbar}{\gamma^* m^* M_U^* G} . \text{ Zero-level for total energy of the mass } m \text{ is set at infinity, while kinetic}$$

energy gained equals the negative gravitational potential energy. The momentum uncertainty is made up by the mass and velocity uncertainties, with the latter one given by the product of acceleration and time uncertainties: $\sqrt{2^*} \sigma_{pU} = \sqrt{2^*} (\sigma_{mU^*} \sigma_{aU^*} \sigma_{tU}) = m_{0^*} \gamma^* a_{U^*} t_U$ and

1 : See annex 6.1. for a derivation of a relativistic Heisenberg uncertainty as applied here.

$\sqrt{2} \cdot \sigma_{xU} = R_U$. With this we gain: $a_{U \geq} \frac{M_U \cdot G}{2 \cdot R_U^2}$ the inertial acceleration that equals gravitational

acceleration due to the equivalence principle, in case of no other forces involved. With the Lorentz factor resulting from the calculated value for σ_{WU} since kinetic energy shows to have the same value

as the rest energy of mass here: $\gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c_0^2}\right)}} = 1 + \frac{\sigma_{WU}}{m_0 \cdot c_0^2} = 2$. For the Universe I assume a

radius $R_U = 4.413 \cdot 10^{26}$ m - equaling 46.65 billion lightyears or 14,300 Mpc [14] - and mass² $M_U = 5.943 \cdot 10^{53}$ kg. With this a zero-point acceleration that cannot be underrun applies to any value of

mass. In case no other forces are present we gain: $g_{zp} = a_U = 1.018 \cdot 10^{-10} \frac{m}{s^2}$. This value is almost

identical to what has been empirically found as a_0 at around $1..1.2 \cdot 10^{-10}$ m/s², the threshold value to invalidity of Newton's law in galaxy observations [9], [15].

To formulate the EQGM I will use the fundamental Planck-units, as introduced in the year 1899 for basic physical quantities [16]. They overcome units created by measures of mankind, e.g. like the „meter“ defined as 1/40,000,000 of the Earth's equatorial perimeter, and are composed only of the key constants to determine relativistic electrodynamics (speed of light $c_0 = 2.99792458 \cdot 10^8$ m/s), gravitation law (gravity constant G), and quantum mechanics (Planck's quantum of action h).

Furthermore Planck-units describe a limit for quantum effects in gravitation, while Planck-mass can be found in setting the Schwarzschild perimeter of a black hole to be equal to its Compton

wavelength [17]: $2 \pi r_s = \lambda_c$ with $r_s = \frac{m_{Pl} \cdot G}{c_0^2}$ and $\lambda_c = \frac{h}{m_{Pl} \cdot c_0}$ this yields:

$$m_{Pl} = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar \cdot c_0}{G}} = 2.176 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ kg} . \text{ Furthermore Planck-length defined as:}$$

$$l_{Pl} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\hbar \cdot G}{c_0^3}\right)} = 1.616 \cdot 10^{-35} \text{ m} \text{ resulting to Planck-time for light traveling along it:}$$

$$t_{Pl} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\hbar \cdot G}{c_0^5}\right)} = 5.391 \cdot 10^{-44} \text{ s} , \text{ and the Planck-energy, exhibiting a value of rest energy for}$$

2 : As part of the problem with DM and DE, the value for the mass of the Universe cannot be exactly known a priori. An explanation for why I do assume the mass of the Universe as stated here is given in section 3.3. .

Planck-mass: $W_{Pl} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\hbar * c_0^5}{G}\right)} = m_{Pl} * c_0^2 = 1.956 \cdot 10^9 J .$

With this I now formulate the Heisenberg uncertainty relation for the mass in the Universe normalized to Planck-units, while introducing a parameter $\alpha > 0$ for multiples of Planck-mass:

$$\left(\sqrt{\left(\frac{\hbar * c_0}{G}\right) * \alpha * \gamma}\right) * \sigma_a * \left(\sqrt{\left(\frac{\hbar * G}{c_0^5}\right) * \frac{1}{\alpha}}\right) * \sigma_x \geq \frac{\hbar}{2} .$$

This yields the same value for the zero-point

acceleration as already calculated above : $a_U \geq \frac{c_0^2}{2 * R_U} = 1.018 \cdot 10^{-10} m/s^2 .$

Comparing the two different expressions derived above for the zero-point acceleration a_U , an

analytical formula for the gravity constant is found: $G = \frac{R_U * c_0^2}{M_U}$. The perspective resulting is, that gravity "constant" appears as a parameter.

The zero-point kinetic energy for the mass in the Universe can also be obtained from the uncertainty relation. Hence for a Planck-mass this is the Planck-energy value as given above, which is resulting there as kinetic energy gained at the boarder of the Universe. Although this is the same value as for the rest energy of mass, it is a kinetic energy appearing on top, since being linked to momentum in the uncertainty relation: $\sqrt{2} * \sigma_{WU}(m) = m_{mb} * \gamma * \sqrt{2} * \sigma_a * R_U = m * c_0^2 = W_{kin}(m) .$

2.1.2. Rest energy uncertainty

For the second case that rest energy fluctuations would make up energy uncertainty, the results are the same as in the section given above, since kinetic and rest energy have been found to be identical. The difference in derivation required is that σ_m is the fluctuating uncertainty with the effective average being equal to mass observed, that would have no fixed value. As a consequence, acceleration σ_a is to be replaced by the fixed value of g_{zp} instead:

$$\sqrt{2} * \sigma_{WU}(m) = \sqrt{2} * \sigma_{mmb} * \gamma * g_{zp} * R_U = m * c_0^2 = W_{kin}(m) .$$

2.2. Gravitational energy potential of the Universe

The model for the gravitational energy potential for a mass in the Universe consists of two regimes: Outside for $R > R_U$ in the vacuum, as already used above, it is hyperbolic:

$W_{gUo}(m, R) = \frac{-m^* M_{U^*} G}{R}$. Inside for $R \leq R_U$ one can assume a homogenous mass density

which is for a mass in intergalactic space, distant from any singularity and thus facing a parabolic

potential: $W_{gUi}(m, R) = \int_{R_U}^R \frac{m^* M_{U^*} G^* (r/R_U)^3}{r^2} dr = \frac{m^* c_0^2}{2} ((R/R_U)^2 - 1)$. As we can see, the

kinetic energy gained from the mass within the homogenous Universe is $\frac{1}{2} m c_0^2$ at maximum on top of the zero-point energy. Exhibit 2 shows the combined gravitational potential for a Planck-mass, including the zero-point energy level, and the hyperbolic potential.

Exh. 2 : A Planck-mass in the Universe

In case of inhomogenous mass distribution, including singularities, the kinetic energy of a mass within the Universe will increase beyond the factor $3/2$ of the value of its rest energy.

From the perspective of mass bodies within the universe these energies cannot be perceived directly for mass bodies in proximity, since they are experiencing the same gravitational and inflationary accelerations, being equal to inertial acceleration due to the equivalence principle.

2.3. Quantization of gravitation

To describe gravitational quantization for a mass body, this shall be done for two cases with regard to hyperbolic potentials describing inhomogenous mass densities and singularities, and for parabolic

potentials describing homogenous mass densities.

2.3.1. Inhomogenous mass density constellations

To describe quantization of interaction between two mass bodies (m;r) and (M;R) in a distance $r_{gB} > r + R$ I use an analogy to proven laws used in atom and solid state physics, namely the quantum model of the Coulomb potential in a hydrogen atom. This has been found by Niels Bohr more than a century ago and explains the stability of atoms due to finite and quantized energy levels arising, despite a hyperbolic singularity potential [18]. Bohr's postulate $p \cdot r \equiv \hbar \cdot n$ with: $n \in N$ is a discretized Heisenberg uncertainty, equaling integer multiples of Planck's quantum of action with the product of momentum and location.

The classical, non-relativistic case

With this, quantized energies and radii are obtained for the electron in the hydrogen atom:

$$W_{qc}(m_e, n) = \frac{-q^2}{8 \cdot \pi \cdot \epsilon_0 \cdot r_B \cdot n^2} = \frac{-W_{kin}(m_e, n)}{2} \quad \text{with } n \in N \quad \text{and Bohr radius: } r_B = \frac{4 \cdot \pi \cdot \epsilon_0 \cdot \hbar^2}{m_e \cdot q^2}$$

With the ground state energy, i.e. ionisation energy level for $n = 1$ as $W_{qc}(m_e) = -13.6 \text{ eV}$ and $r_B = 0.53 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ m}$.

Now I transfer this to a model for gravitation between mass bodies. Since Coulomb and gravitation force laws are similar related to the formula above, except for a factor $G / (8 \pi \epsilon_0)$ and charge q^2 to be replaced by the product of mass m and M , we gain:

$$\frac{W_{gpot}(m, M, n)}{2} = \frac{-m \cdot M \cdot G}{2 \cdot r_{gB} \cdot n^2} = \frac{-m^3 \cdot M^2 \cdot G^2}{2 \cdot \hbar^2 \cdot n^2} = -\frac{W_{kin}(m, M, n)}{2} \quad \text{with } n \in N \quad \text{and a}$$

“gravitational Bohr radius”: $r_{gB}(m, M) = \frac{\hbar^2}{m^2 \cdot M \cdot G}$.

In the three-dimensional spherical Bohr atom model, each energy state n can be occupied with a maximum of $2 \cdot n^2$ fermionic mass bodies, hence resulting to a total number of quantum states available of $2 \cdot n^3$. Hence N mass bodies confined in a sphere with radius R will occupy the states up to the highest kinetic energy known as the Fermi energy [19] adding on top of the zero-point energy

level: $W_F = \frac{\hbar^2}{2 \cdot m} \cdot \left(\frac{3 \cdot \pi^2 \cdot N}{4/3 \cdot \pi \cdot R^3} \right)^{\frac{2}{3}}$.

The relativistic case

For this, a relativistic Bohr postulate with the Lorentz factor to consider increase of inertia in the inertial system of the Universe (U) and contraction of length in the inertial system of the mass body (mb) on the circular trajectory to meet the quantization criteria is set up:

$$p_{U^*} r_{mb} = m^* \gamma^* v_{U^*} r_{U^*} \gamma^{-1} \equiv \hbar^* n \quad \text{with:} \quad n \in N .$$

For the velocity of the mass body is gained from the formula for relativistic kinetic energy:

$$W_{kinr} = (\gamma - 1) m^* c_0^2 \implies v_U = c_0 \sqrt{\left(1 - \frac{1}{(1 + \beta^2)^2}\right)} \quad \text{with} \quad \beta^2 = \frac{W_{kinr}}{m^* c_0^2} .$$

After simplification possible for $\beta \gg 1$ this yields for the relativistic gravitational Bohr radius in

the inertial system of the Universe: $r_{gBr}(m) = \frac{\hbar}{m^* c_0}$ and for the kinetic energy³ of mass m:

$$W_{kinr}(m, n) = \frac{m^2 * M^* G^* c_0}{n^* \hbar} . \text{ For the case that the mass body is at } r = R_U, \text{ i.e. } \beta = 1, \text{ it is:}$$

$$r_{gBr}(m) = \frac{2^* \hbar}{\sqrt{3^*} m^* c_0}, \text{ and for kinetic energy: } W_{kinr}(m, n) = \frac{\sqrt{3^*} m^2 * M^* G^* c_0}{2^* n^* \hbar} .$$

Applied to a mass body within the Universe we find a formula which can be interpreted as containing a quantum exchange particle I call ‘‘Ghton’’ (Gh) in analogy to a Photon since it seems to be moving with the speed of light:

$$W_{kinrU}(m, n) = \frac{(m^* c_0^2)^2}{n_{Gr^*} W_{Gh}} = W_{Gr}(m, n) \quad \text{with} \quad W_{Gh}(R_U) = \frac{\hbar^* c_0}{R_U} = 7.171 \cdot 10^{-53} J .$$

For the quantized energy state levels let us call these quasi-particles ‘‘Gravons’’ (Gr), with n_{Gr} the Grapon quantum number. This is in analogy to the Phonon, the quasi-particle for the energy states of collective atom oscillations in solid state crystals [19].

The corresponding de Broglie wavelength of the Ghton is $\lambda_{Gh} = 2^* \pi^* R_U = 2.77 \cdot 10^{27} m$ with a frequency of $f_{Gh} = 1.081 \cdot 10^{-19} Hz$, and can be thought of as spanning along the perimeter of the Universe. For the matter waves to be associated to the relativistic Gravons it can be written:

$$\lambda_{Gr}(m, n_{Gr}) = \frac{\hbar^* c_0}{W_{kr}(n_{Gr})} = \frac{2^* \pi^* r_{gBr^*} n_{Gr^*} W_{Gh}}{W_0} \quad \text{with:} \quad W_0 = m^* c_0^2 . \text{ For example for a Planck-mass}$$

3 : With this one finds, that relativistic effects $W_{kinr} > m^* c_0^2$ apply if $m^* M > m_{pl}^2$.

at the boarder of the Universe we can calculate:

$$r_{gBr} := R_U \implies n_{Gr}(m_{Pl}, R_U) = \frac{R_U^* m_{Pl}^* c_0}{\hbar} = 2.731 \cdot 10^{61} .$$

As a consequence, for smaller mass bodies, there must be limit, thus otherwise these would have to occupy states also outside the Universe in the hyperbolic continuum – similar to what is known from the Chandrasekhar limit for white dwarf stars [20]. In contrary, for larger mass bodies the available quantum states will only be merely filled-up. In the relativistic case the Fermi energy adding on top of the zero-point energy level is based on the relativistic momentum and de Broglie wavelength, with N the number of mass bodies:

$$W_{Fr} = \hbar * \pi * c_0 * \left(\frac{3 * N}{4/3 * \pi^2 * R^3} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} = W_{Gh} * \left(\frac{9 * \pi * N}{4} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} .$$

From the relativistic gravitational Bohr formula we can also interpret a minimum for the mass required for a mass body to exist in the current Universe:

$$n_{Gr} := 1 \implies m_{minU} = \frac{\hbar}{R_U^* c_0} = \frac{W_{Gh}}{c_0^2} = 7.970 \cdot 10^{-70} \text{ kg} .$$

Finally, a minimum for the size of Universe from current perspective could be hypothesized, if groundstate $n_{Gr} = 1$ with Ghotons acting between two halves of the mass of current Universe is

assumed⁴: $n_{Gr} := 1 \implies R_{U00} = \frac{\hbar}{4 * M_U^* c_0} = 1.480 \cdot 10^{-97} \text{ m} .$

2.3.2. Homogenous mass density constellations

For a Universe with homogenous mass density, the mass bodies are confined in the parabolic potential according to Exhibit 2, and the relativistic case does apply:

$$W_{kr}(m, n_{Gr}) = m * c_0^2 * \left(\frac{3}{2} - \frac{1}{2} * \left(\frac{r(n_{Gr})}{R_U} \right)^2 \right) \quad \text{with:} \quad r(n_{Gr}) = n_{Gr} * r_{gBr} = n_{Gr} * \frac{\hbar}{m * c_0} . \text{ This can be}$$

reformulated to: $W_{kr}(m, n_{Gr}) = W_0 * \left(\frac{3}{2} - \frac{1}{2} * n_{Gr}^2 * \left(\frac{W_{Gh}}{W_0} \right)^2 \right) \quad \text{with:} \quad W_0 = m * c_0^2 .$ For example for a

Planck-mass for n_{Grzp} the kinetic energy level will be at zero-point:

4 : See also annex 6.3. for further approaches to assess a minimum size for the Universe.

$$n_{Grzp}(m_{Pl}) = \frac{R_U}{r_{gBr}} = \frac{m_{Pl}^* c_0^2}{W_{Gh}} = 2.731 \cdot 10^{61} \quad \Rightarrow \quad W_{kr}(m_{Pl}, n_{Grzp}) = W_{zp}(m_{Pl}) = m_{Pl}^* c_0^2.$$

To the relativistic Gravon energies, matter wavelengths do result in the range of 10^{-34} m and related

$$\text{frequencies in the range of } 10^{42} \text{ Hz: } \lambda_{Gr}(m, n_{Gr}) = \frac{\hbar^* c_0}{W_{kr}(n_{Gr})} = \frac{2^* \pi^* r_{gBr}}{\frac{3}{2} - \frac{1}{2^*} n_{Gr}^2 \left(\frac{W_{Gh}}{W_0} \right)^2}.$$

2.3.3. Quantum state occupation and particles in the Universe

Since gravitation applies to all and between all mass bodies in the Universe, to determine quantum state occupation and degree of degeneracy⁵ indicated by Fermi energy as compared to the depth of the homogenous Universe parabolic quantum well, the size of the smallest elementary mass particle(s) and their volume(s) in the Universe have to be known as well. As can be seen for the artificial case of a Universe with Planck-mass as elementary particles, these would be far from degeneracy:

$$W_{FrPl} = 4.140 \cdot 10^{-32} \text{ J} \quad \text{vs.} \quad W_{potU} = \frac{1}{2^*} m_{Pl}^* c_0^2 = 9.78 \cdot 10^8 \text{ J} \quad \text{with:} \quad N_{Pl} = \frac{M_U}{m_{Pl}} = 2.731 \cdot 10^{61}.$$

An elementary mass particle filling all available quantum states in the Universe would exhibit degenerate matter pressure and thus drive expansion of the Universe, as initially described in [21].

With this one can calculate mass and volume of such particle required, if it would have to make up missing DM with $\Omega_{DM} = \Omega_M - \Omega_b = 0.315 - 0.049 = 0.266$:

$$W_{Fr00} := \frac{1}{2^*} m_{00}^* c_0^2 \quad \Rightarrow \quad m_{00} = \left(\frac{2^* \hbar^* \pi}{c_0} \right)^{\frac{3}{4}} \left(\frac{9}{4^*} \frac{M_U^* \Omega_{DM} / \Omega_b}{\pi^2 R_U^3} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}}. \quad \text{This yields:}$$

$$m_{00} = 1.743 \cdot 10^{-38} \text{ kg} \quad \text{and:} \quad N_{00} = \frac{M_U^* \Omega_{DM} / \Omega_b}{m_{00}} = 1.851 \cdot 10^{92}. \quad \text{Thus the corresponding rest}$$

energy, average kinetic energy and black body radiation temperature of the particle would be:

$$W_{00} = m_{00}^* c_0^2 = 9.780 \text{ meV} \quad \text{and} \quad W_{km} = \frac{3}{5^*} W_{Fr00} = 2.934 \text{ meV} \quad \text{and} \quad T_{00} = 12.067 \text{ K}$$

The candidate for this is the Neutrino as the particle with yet unknown, but smallest mass of all elementary particles in the Universe known so far. It is assumed with the highest particle density in

5 : An alternative formulation for degeneracy is that mass body distance be smaller than the corresponding de Broglie wavelength of the mass body, which is far from being the case for nucleons in the current Universe and any mass larger than this.

the Universe. However, since the Neutrino temperature in the observed Cosmic Neutrino Background (CNB) is only 1.945 K [11] and its appearance is assumed “only” a billion times higher ($n_\nu = 340 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and $N_\nu = 1.22 \cdot 10^{89}$) than the number of nucleons in the Universe, it can contribute less than one percentage point to missing DM.

To conclude, to date no elementary particle could be identified as a candidate to explain extra mass required for DM.

3. Results and discussion of the EQGM

In reality mass bodies in the Universe will mostly differ, offsetting the minimum energy level for each value of mass as can be seen from the expression for the Graviton energy above. Moreover, the Universe is only partially homogenous at scale, but made of clusters of galaxies, solar systems, stars, planets, dust, gas etc. as local structures, all of them representing gravitational potential wells. This leads to coupled potentials of different size. Superposition of quantum states can be assumed to lead to split-up of energy states into quasi-continuums for the body systems being in proximity, as this is well-known for electrons in the coulomb potentials in solid state crystals. Concluding, we can assume that every mass body is finding an unoccupied energy state in the current Universe. Note that the model above has not comprised dynamic excitation and recombination effects in the quantum statistics.

Hence quantization effects in the motion of mass bodies may become obvious under some circumstances - as for example with the zero-point acceleration in intergalactic space at the outer range of galaxies - but not be perceived due to tiny Ghoton energies between Gravitons and/or continuum effects in most other cases.

The EQGM derived above does not necessarily require the existence of a space beyond the radius of the Universe. This is since I have described the EQGM also based on a quantum mechanical potential well perspective from within the Universe.

3.1. Explanation for Dark Matter effect – A quantum gravitation force law

In a galaxy Newton gravitational acceleration is imposed on any body with: $g_N(r) = \frac{M_{Gx^*} G}{r^2}$. The gravitational zero-point acceleration of the Universe will be acting as superposition on top:

$$g_{QGM}(r) = g_N(r) + g_{zp}$$

Comparing the new quantum gravitation law to the given MOND models gained empirically by

fitting to observation [9], we find congruence. See Exhibit 1 for a typical galaxy with 10^{11} sun mass:

$M_{Gx} = 1.988 \cdot 10^{41}$ kg. The MOND fit models [15] are $g_{MOND}(r) = \frac{M_{Gx} \cdot G}{\mu\left(\frac{g_N(r)}{a_0}\right) \cdot r^2}$ with assuming

$a_0 = 1.1 \cdot 10^{-10}$ m/s² and the parameters: $\mu_1(x) = \frac{1}{1+x}$ and proposed alternatively: $\mu_2(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1+x^2}}$.

Exh. 1: Gravitational Acceleration

Hence DM assumption that is used to explain additional gravitational acceleration in the outer regimes of galaxies is not required here due to zero-point acceleration acting on all mass bodies being confined in the Universe⁶.

3.2. Explanation for Dark Energy and accelerated expansion of the Universe

The zero-point energy described above causes a repulsive (i.e. expansive) pressure to the Universe

⁶ : See section 3.8. for explanation why the zero-point acceleration is attractive. See annex 6.5. for a brief analyses of failing inflation-based gravitational acceleration explanation approaches for galaxies.

as contained in an outside vacuum, while acting against the attracting gravitational forces.

Accordingly this energy is a candidate to explain DE.

At the border of the universe at $r = R_U$ the pressure is made up by the kinetic zero-point energy of a “mass body fluid” in the Universe itself. The DE is appearing in the Universe as the kinetic expansion energy of masses as perceived by any observer witnessing inflation.

The relativistic radial expansive pressure is: $P_{\text{exp}} = \frac{-W_{zpU}}{4/3 \pi R_U^3} = \frac{-M_U c_0^2}{4/3 \pi R_U^3} = -\rho_U c_0^2$. The

gravitational, deflationary pressure calculated with the hydrostatic approach is⁷:

$$P_{gU}(R_U) = \int_0^{R_U} \rho(r) g_U(r) dr = \frac{1}{2} \rho_U c_0^2. \quad \text{Hence an effective pressure of :}$$

$$\Delta P = P_{\text{exp}} + P_{gU} = P_{\text{exp}} + P_{gN} + P_{gZP} = -\frac{1}{2} \rho_U c_0^2 = -0.742 \cdot 10^{-10} \frac{N}{m^2} \quad \text{acting like a „negative}$$

gravitational“ acceleration, and an acceleration for the scale parameter a does result at the boarder of the Universe:

$$\Delta g = \frac{\Delta P \cdot 4 \pi R_U^2}{M_U} = \frac{-3 c_0^2}{2 R_U} = -\frac{3}{2} a_U = -3.055 \cdot 10^{-10} \frac{m}{s^2} \quad \text{and: } \ddot{a} = \frac{-\Delta g}{R_U} = 6.921 \cdot 10^{-37} s^{-2}.$$

Related to the notation used in the current Standard Model of Cosmology (Λ -CDM model) with w being the DE factor in the equation of state, this results to $w = -1$ in line with observations from [10] and with ESA Planck results [11], as well as with WMAP results [14].

From the EQGM - considering classical Newton and on top zero-point gravitational acceleration - the DE density $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.666$ is two-fold of the gravitational energy density attached to the mass of the Universe $\Omega_M = 0.333$, while assuming that energy densities from radiation Ω_r and curvature of space Ω_K can be neglected.

ESA Planck results from Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) analysis exhibit $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.685$ and $\Omega_M = 0.315$ (+/- 0.007), if Ω_K is set to zero. With the extended Λ -CDM model, Ω_K is found there around 0.025 (+/- 0.02) [11], with this hence EQGM results being in line for Ω_M and Ω_Λ .

For the case that energy densities were analysed based on observations of galaxy lensing, i.e. with underlying gravitation effects far beyond the zero point gravitational acceleration, ESA Planck [11]

⁷ : Note, that other as with kinetic expansive pressure, the inner gravitational binding energy cannot be taken to calculate gravitational pressure taking effect on the border of the Universe – see annex 6.5. .

and WMAP results [14] are found in the regimes around $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.73$ and $\Omega_M = 0.27$. This points to the case that zero-point gravitational acceleration partial pressure:

$$P_{gzp} = \frac{g_{zp} * M_U}{4 * \pi * R_U^2} = \frac{\frac{c_0^2}{2 * R_U} * M_U}{4 * \pi * R_U^2} = \frac{\rho_U}{6} * c_0^2$$

would have to be skipped in calculation of ΔP above if not determining the observation, which would lead to a ratio of 3:1 for $\Omega_\Lambda : \Omega_M$ from EQGM.

To conclude, the EQGM can also provide an explanation for DE, while relative precision based on currently available observations is in the interval of +/- 0.03 for the energy densities.

Consequently in the EQGM the total on top energy appearing in the Universe is:

$W_{Uzp} = M_U * c_0^2 = 5.341 \cdot 10^{70} \text{ J} = DE = DM * c_0^2$. Obviously the equivalent mass associated with this DE is the mass of the Universe M_U itself, which thus is also acting as DM.

3.3. Implications on and from the Gravity constant

Comparing the two different expressions derived above for the zero-point acceleration σ_a , an

analytical formula for the gravity constant was found: $G = \frac{R_U * c_0^2}{M_U}$. Thus gravity "constant" appears

as a parameter. It depends on radius and mass of the Universe, at least here is no requirement for the more exceptional case that it be a fundamental constant of nature. Hence G will change over time in a non-stationary Universe, if the ratio R_U / M_U is not constant. Moreover, this would feed back on former and further evolution, leading to non-linear effects. However, regardless of how R_U and M_U evolve, they cancel out in the calculation for the kinetic zero-point energy⁸ of a mass in the Universe, that thus will always be identical to the value of its rest energy.

Due to the problem of DM and DE the exact value of mass M_U was unknown so far. However, since I found the formula above which is confirmed by the identity of calculated and observed zero-point acceleration, the mass M_U can be calculated out of it, if a value for radius R_U is assumed.

To what extend would mankind have been able to observe a change in G over the course of research, i.e. time T_{Go} from year 1798 to 2023? The answer is: Not at all, assuming a change of its radius based on the Hubble expansion [11] of:

$$\Delta G = H_0 * T_{Go} = 1.551 \cdot 10^{-8} \quad \text{with:} \quad H_0 = 67.4 \frac{\text{km/s}}{\text{Mpc}} = 2.184 \cdot 10^{-18} * s^{-1}$$

8 : Based on the formula in section 2.1.1. while inserting the formula for G out of this section.

measured values for G being three orders of magnitude larger [4].

The formula for G is also the event horizon of a classical stationary finite low density black hole. However which is different from a dark star black hole that would exhibit a Schwarzschild radius r_s as its event horizon, which is double the value of r_{bh} [22]. Hence mass of the Universe M_U might be increased from outside of it. However, looking at the critical mass density required to form a black hole, the Universe is below this with regard to its average density:

$$\rho_U = \frac{M_U}{4/3 \pi R_U^3} = 1.650 \cdot 10^{-27} \text{ kg m}^{-3} \text{ versus: } \rho_{Cr} = \frac{3 H_0^2}{8 \pi G} = 8.533 \cdot 10^{-27} \text{ kg m}^{-3} .$$

3.4. Gravitational zero-point fluctuations

With the EQGM derived above, zero-point kinetic energy of a mass in the Universe has a value equal to its rest energy, but appearing on top. It can be understood in a classical manner as self-energy rooted in the gravitational potential of the Universe, and in a quantum mechanical view as being required from the Heisenberg uncertainty due to confinement in its potential. However, how can this relatively high on top energy and the attached zero-point acceleration for mass bodies be understood and why is it not observed directly? Key to understand is the quite short Planck-time scale t_{Pl}/α in which uncertainty is taking place. In case of absence of other forces we can also calculate the fluctuation kinetic energy W_{fluc} and a zero-point fluctuation distance r_{fluc} that is caused for the non-localized mass - since $\sqrt{2} \sigma_{xU} = R_U$ - with probability distribution spread across the Universe: $W_{fluc}(m) = 1/2 \cdot m \cdot (g_{zp} \cdot t_{Pl}/\alpha)^2$ and $r_{fluc}(m) = 1/2 \cdot g_{zp} \cdot (t_{Pl}/\alpha)^2$. With using equations derived here before, this can be written as:

$$W_{fluc}(m) = \frac{\hbar \cdot m_{Pl}^2 \cdot c_0}{8 \cdot m \cdot R_U \cdot M_U} = \frac{W_{Gh}}{8} \cdot \frac{m_{Pl}^2}{m \cdot M_U} = m \cdot c_0^2 \cdot \frac{r_{fluczp}}{2 \cdot R_U} \implies W_{fluc}(m_{Pl}) = 3.279 \cdot 10^{-115} \text{ J}$$

$$\text{and } r_{fluc}(m) = \frac{\hbar \cdot m_{Pl}^2}{4 \cdot M_U \cdot c_0 \cdot m^2} = \frac{r_{gBr}}{4} \cdot \frac{m_{Pl}^2}{m \cdot M_U} \implies r_{fluc}(m_{Pl}) = 1.480 \cdot 10^{-97} \text{ m}$$

demonstrating that this fluctuation energy is too tiny to be observed directly. However, energy density of the fluctuations in the spherical shell with thickness $r_{fluc}/3$ is identical as for the zero-point energy of the mass body related to the entire Universe:

$$w_{fluc} = \frac{W_{fluc}}{4 \pi R_U^2 \cdot r_{fluc}/3} = \frac{m \cdot c_0^2}{4/3 \pi R_U^3} = w_{zp} .$$

3.5. Gravitational quantum particles and matter waves

First gravitational particles were assumed by Pierre-Simon Laplace more than two centuries ago, while a quantum mechanical particle named Graviton was first mentioned in the 20th century. In the diverse set of quantum gravity approaches the Graviton is mostly – but not always - assumed to be the exchange quantum of gravitation. However, also further particles were proposed in the history of quantum gravity approaches, like Gravitino, Goldstino, Sgoldstino, Gravissskalar and Gravivektor [23].

In the EQGM each mass body in the Universe has a quantized gravitational energy state – dubbed with the quasi-particle name “Gravon” – and a de Broglie matter wave [24] associated. The gravitational effect is assumed to be realized via the quantum exchange particle dubbed Ghoton, assumed to move at the speed of light. For a mass body to change its gravitational energy, i.e. Gravon state, Ghotons have to be emitted to decrease or absorbed to increase its gravitational energy, respectively.

Both, Ghoton and Gravon, quantum particle energies are inversely proportional to the confinement space, i.e. the distance between interacting mass bodies. In case of interaction considered between a mass and the entire mass of the Universe this is the radius of the Universe R_U .

With regard to gravitational coupling significant effects have to be expected due to relativistic kinetic zero-point energy of mass in the Universe – for the derivation of a gravitational coupling parameter see annex 6.4. .

To conclude, in the EQGM the Ghoton is the exchange particle to play the role of the Graviton, while the Gravon is a quasi-particle representing the matter waves associated with DE and DM.

3.6. Quantization of time for a mass

With introducing and using the Planck-time to explain DE and DM, the question arises how to interpret implications on uncertainty of time as a parameter in physical processes as such. If we assume, that any physical interaction of a mass with its environment requires time to evolve, it can be hypothesized that a minimum granularity of time for a mass body could be:

$$\sigma_{IU}(m)^* \sqrt{2} \geq \frac{t_{Pl}}{\alpha} = \frac{t_{Pl}^* m_{Pl}}{m} = \frac{\hbar}{m^* c_0^2} = \tau_{fluc}(m) .$$

For example for an electron this would result

to a granularity in the range of 10^{-21} s, and for the smallest particle known so far, the Neutrino, it presumably could be in the range of $10^{-12}..10^{-15}$ s.

For the minimum mass of a mass body required to exist in the Universe - as derived above - we

gain: $\sigma_{tU}(m_{minU})^* \sqrt{2} = \frac{\hbar}{\frac{\hbar}{R_U^* c_0^2}} = \frac{R_U}{c_0} = 46.65 \text{ bn yrs}$. This appears to be logical in the sense

that a mass in the Universe can only be noticed if it at least once in the time the Universe is existing⁹ would become part of any physical process.

3.7. Zero-gravitation and degree of quantization

Considering more compact potential wells with homogenous mass density than the Universe, there has to be a limit where Graviton groundstate energy level will become equal or higher than the depth of the respective gravitational potential well. This means that gravitation effect of a mass body (m;r) in a homogenous mass density “cloud” (M_C;R_C) would vanish, if:

$$W_{Gr0}(R_C) = \frac{\hbar^* c_0}{2^* R_C} \geq \frac{1}{2^*} \frac{m^* M_C^* G}{R_C} = \frac{1}{2^*} m^* c_0^2 \eta \quad \text{with: } \eta = \frac{R_U}{R_C} \frac{M_C}{M_U} .$$

While η is a scale factor to re-normalize zero-point energy of mass in the Universe towards the interaction of mass with the cloud. Reformulating the inequation yields:

$$m^* M_C \leq \frac{\hbar^* M_U}{c_0^* R_U} \quad \text{with: } \sqrt{\left(\frac{\hbar^* M_U}{c_0^* R_U}\right)} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\hbar^* c_0}{G}\right)} = 2.176 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ m} = m_{Pl} .$$

This means: For a body with product of its mass and cloud's mass being less than the square of the Planck-mass, the gravitation effect should vanish.

Another setup arises for two mass bodies (m;r) and (M;R) in distance $d > r + R$ interacting with each other. The non-relativistic gravitational Bohr model¹⁰ as derived above and groundstate energy

level (n = 1) yield: $r_{gB} = \frac{\hbar^2}{m^2 M^* G} \equiv d \implies m^2 M = \frac{\hbar^2}{d^* G}$. From this three cases do arise:

Case 1: Significant quantization effects should be observed, if distance of mass bodies is equal or in the range of gravitational Bohr radius. For example this is given for a distance of $d = 6 \text{ cm}$ between a mass of 1 gram and a neutron. Another example would be between two identical mass bodies with $1.4 \cdot 10^{-19} \text{ kg}$ at this distance.

9 : Obviously this is not the age of the Universe since it has expanded from presumed big bang event and $R_H < R_U$ today. However, the argument for a mass to become part of a physical process at least once needs to apply to entire Universe.

10 : To use the non-relativistic gravitational Bohr formulas, $m^*M < m_{Pl}^2$ has to apply, as in the three case examples here.

Case 2: For a distance less than the gravitational Bohr radius gravitation effect should vanish, since energy cannot be decreased below groundstate at $n = 1$.

Case 3: For the distance significantly larger than gravitational Bohr radius, gravitation effect should approach a continuum, i.e. quantization cannot be resolved in observation anymore.

From this we can conclude that zero-gravitation and quantization effects should be considered for the study of formation processes of objects in the Universe converging out of gas, dust and micro particles, which is for further study.

Apart from this, bodies will experience gravitation effects from with all other objects in the Universe, and including its zero-point acceleration as described in the section 3.1. above.

3.8. Quantum origin of gravitation and inertial Equivalence Principle

A generalized law for gravitational energy and acceleration for two mass bodies m and M separated by a distance r in the Universe can be described, if quantization reaches continuum, as:

$$W_{\text{pot}}(m, M, r) = \frac{-m^* M^* G}{r} = -\eta^* m^* c_0^2 \quad \text{with:} \quad \eta = \frac{R_U}{r} \frac{M}{M_U} \quad \text{since:} \quad G = \frac{R_U^* c_0^2}{M_U}$$

With η being the scale factor to re-normalize respective confinement of mass bodies and size of mass related to properties of the Universe.

Now I consider the two mass bodies as confining each other in the Universe and describe them in Heisenberg uncertainties used as equations, hence realizing minimum energy possible. With

$$\text{uncertainties as: } \sigma_x = \frac{r}{\sqrt{2}} \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_p = \frac{p}{\sqrt{2}} \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad p = \frac{\hbar}{r} \quad \text{and}$$

$$\sigma_{W^*} \sqrt{2} = -W_{\text{pot}} = W_{\text{kin}} = \eta^* m^* c_0^2 \quad \Rightarrow \quad \sigma_{t^*} \sqrt{2} = \frac{\hbar}{\eta^* m^* c_0^2}. \quad \text{With this we gain for the force and}$$

$$\text{acceleration}^{11} \text{ between the two mass bodies: } \frac{\sigma_p}{\sigma_t} = F = m^* a = m^* \frac{\eta^* c_0^2}{r} = m^* c_0^2 \frac{R_U}{r^2} \frac{M}{M_U}. \quad \text{The}$$

force is attractive since momentum p increases with decreasing distance r due to Heisenberg uncertainty relation.

The perspective for gravitation is, that it originates from an instability contained in the quantum

11 : For a body on the surface of the Earth for example the expected acceleration value is gained:

$$a_E = \frac{\eta_E^* c_0^2}{R_E} = c_0^2 \frac{R_U}{R_E^2} \frac{M_E}{M_U} = \frac{(2.998 \cdot 10^8 \text{ m/s})^2 \cdot 4.413 \cdot 10^{26} \text{ m} \cdot 5.972 \cdot 10^{24} \text{ kg}}{(6.366 \cdot 10^6 \text{ m})^2 \cdot 5.943 \cdot 10^{53} \text{ kg}} = 9.835 \text{ m/s}^2$$

mechanical uncertainty, maximizing confined momentum and minimizing distance between mass bodies. As we see it is based on inertia, explaining the equivalence principle of inertial and gravitational acceleration: Here we find no such special thing like a „gravitational acceleration” being different from inertia.

3.9. Summary of gravitational energy interpretations

I want to summarize the different appearances of energies related to gravity used in the EQGM. It was found that there is an identity of the energies attached to mass:

$$- W_{\text{spot}}(m) = W_{\text{kin}}(m) = m \cdot c_0^2 = \sigma_{WU} \cdot \sqrt{2} = m \cdot \gamma \cdot \sigma_a \cdot \sqrt{2} \cdot R_U = \sigma_{m^*} \cdot \sqrt{2} \cdot \gamma \cdot g_{zp} \cdot R_U . \text{ With:}$$

- *Newton gravitational potential energy*, as negative identity for the gravitational kinetic energy of the mass related to at $r = R_U$ as the boarder of the Universe.
- *Rest energy of mass* according to Einstein's Equivalence Principle, which leads to use mass and energy synonymous in the General Relativity Theory as Energy-Momentum Tensor [3].
- *Quantum mechanical uncertainty zero-point energy* for mass, as shown in this work. This energy can be interpreted as fluctuations on a time scale τ_{fluc} in two ways:
 - As a so called “Zitterbewegung”, a phenomenon first described in [25] for electrons. In this work it is found to cause zero-point acceleration for mass bodies appearing as gravitational acceleration g_{zp} and rooted in kinetic energy fluctuations, with $\gamma = 2$:

$$\sigma_{WU} \cdot \sqrt{2} := W_{\text{kin}} = (\gamma - 1) \cdot m \cdot c_0^2 \Rightarrow \sigma_{tU} \cdot \sqrt{2} = \frac{\hbar}{m \cdot c_0^2} = \tau_{\text{fluc}} .$$

- As “mass-defect energy fluctuations”, where zero-point energy is temporarily created out

$$\text{of mass and vice versa: } \sigma_{WU} \cdot \sqrt{2} := W_{\text{rest}} = m \cdot c_0^2 \Rightarrow \sigma_{tU} \cdot \sqrt{2} = \frac{\hbar}{m \cdot c_0^2} = \tau_{\text{fluc}} .$$

To summarize, the physical parameters of mass, rest energy of mass, negative gravitational potential and attached zero-point kinetic energy, as well as quantum zero-point energy are found here to be equivalent representations to describe gravitation. Moreover, the zero-point kinetic energy of a mass body in the Universe is found to be on-top of the rest energy, and invariant with regard to total mass and radius of the Universe.

4. Conclusions

The relatively simple EQGM looking at the Universe as composed of quantum wells delivers qualitative and quantitative explanation approaches for effects associated with DM and DE, in line with observations. Furthermore it shows, that gravity can be described as a quantum mechanical effect as such. The total on top energy appearing in the EQGM for the Universe is: $W_{Uzp} = M_U * c_0^2 = 5.341 \cdot 10^{70} J = DE = DM * c_0^2$. Obviously the mass equivalent associated with this DE is the mass of the Universe M_U itself, which thus is also acting as DM. Hence, a DM as a kind of so far unknown mass is not required since the gravitational zero-point acceleration has been identified to explain the effect of observed galaxy rotation violation.

For the gravitational quantum effects that should exhibit discrete effects as discussed above, further study is required to design analyses and experiments for validation.

Given the vast diversity and history of research in the field of quantum gravity done in the last decades, it must be beyond the scope of this work to discuss and assess the EQGM as compared to the variety of approaches.

Moreover, it is left for further study how the EQGM and its findings can help to also better understand the evolution of the Universe, even deeper towards the origin and its destination.

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6. Annex

6.1. Relativistic Heisenberg uncertainty relation

The Heisenberg Uncertainty relation shall be described for an inertial system of the Universe (U), with the mass moving with velocity v in it, and in the inertial system of the mass body itself (mb),

where the mass is at rest. The Lorentz factor is described as: $\gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c_0^2}\right)}}$. To generalize, I do

not exclude any of the physical parameters from uncertainty and hence do allow variance for all of them, leading to the generic form: $\sigma_m^* \sigma_a^* \sigma_t^* \sigma_x \geq \frac{\hbar}{2}$. For the analyses the length and time scales from the inertial system of the Universe will be considered.

To recapitulate, the following rules from Special Relativity Theory apply for two inertial systems moving with relative velocity v to each other [26]:

- Relativistic increase of inertia increases momentum and energy of the mass body observed in the inertial system of the Universe, as described by the Lorentz factor
- Time scales of the observed other inertial system appear slower, i.e. decreased (time dilation)
- Length scales of the observed other inertial system appear reduced (length contraction)
- Time and length scales observed within each inertial system appear unchanged, thus also velocity and acceleration within each inertial system appear unchanged
- Hence the relative velocities of inertial systems to each other are observed at the same value in both systems

The Heisenberg uncertainty applies for both inertial systems as:

$$\sigma_{pU}^* \sigma_{xU} \geq \frac{\hbar}{2} \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_{WU}^* \sigma_{tU} \geq \frac{\hbar}{2} \quad \text{and:} \quad \sigma_{pmb}^* \sigma_{xmb} \geq \frac{\hbar}{2} \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_{Wmb}^* \sigma_{tmb} \geq \frac{\hbar}{2} .$$

The actual physical parameter and its variance are related so that Heisenberg uncertainty set as equation matches the groundstate $n = 1$ of Bohr's postulate:

$$p \cdot r \equiv \hbar \cdot n \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad \sigma_p \cdot \sigma_x = \frac{\hbar}{2} \quad \Rightarrow \quad \sigma_p = \frac{p}{\sqrt{2}} \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_x = \frac{x}{\sqrt{2}} \quad \text{with:} \quad x = r$$

Consequently for energy and time uncertainty it is: $\sigma_W = \frac{W}{\sqrt{2}}$ and $\sigma_t = \frac{t}{\sqrt{2}}$.

Thus, for the inertial system of the Universe the momentum, the effective inertia and kinetic energy of the mass body resting in its inertial system (mb) have to be adapted by the Lorentz factor. The uncertainty of energy can be rooted in the rest energy or in the kinetic energy :

$$\sigma_{pU} = \sigma_{mU} \cdot \sigma_{aU} \cdot \sigma_{tU} = \frac{p_U}{\sqrt{2}} \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_{WU} = \sigma_{mU} \cdot \sigma_{aU} \cdot \sigma_{xU} = \frac{W_{rest}}{\sqrt{2}} \quad \text{or} \quad = \frac{W_{kin}}{\sqrt{2}} .$$

For the energy and momentum the relativistic relations have to be taken, note that relativistic energy contains the rest energy, while momentum is zero at rest:

$$W_U = m_U \cdot c_0^2 = m_{mb} \cdot \gamma \cdot c_0^2 = W_{rest} + W_{kinU} = m_{mb} \cdot c_0^2 + m_{mb} \cdot (\gamma - 1) \cdot c_0^2 \quad \text{with:} \quad m_{mb} = m$$

$$, \text{ and } p_U = \sqrt{\left(\left(\frac{W_U}{c_0} \right)^2 - \left(m_U \cdot c_0 \right)^2 \right)} = m_{mb} \cdot \gamma \cdot v_U = m_U \cdot a_U \cdot t_U .$$

For the inertial system of the mass body (mb) the time and length scale of the Universe have to be adapted by the Lorentz factor:

$$\sigma_{pmb} = \sigma_{mmb} \cdot \sigma_{amb} \cdot \sigma_{tmb} \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_{xmb} = \sigma_{xU} \cdot \gamma^{-1} .$$

$$\sigma_{Wmb} = \sigma_{mmb} \cdot \sigma_{amb} \cdot \sigma_{xmb} \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_{tmb} = \sigma_{tU} \cdot \gamma .$$

6.2. Expansion of the Universe using the Friedman equation

I set up the Friedman equation [27] for a flat Universe according to the Standard Model of Cosmology (Λ -Cold Dark Matter-CDM), while considering the on-top gravitational zero point acceleration as derived in the EQGM. Hence mass density ρ_U and the expansive pressure P_{exp} are assumed as:

$$\rho_U(r) = \frac{M_U}{4/3 \cdot \pi \cdot r^3} \quad P_{exp}(r) = \frac{-W_{zpU}}{4/3 \cdot \pi \cdot r^3} \quad G = \frac{R_U \cdot c_0^2}{M_U} \quad \text{with:} \quad W_{zpU} = M_U \cdot c_0^2$$

With $a(r)$ being a scale factor for the radius of the Universe and $a = 1$ for the current state:

$a(r) = \frac{r}{R_U}$. The Friedman equation with \ddot{a} being the second derivative for the scale factor $a(r)$

with respect to time, this means normalized acceleration thus can be written as:

$$\ddot{a}(r) = a(r) \cdot \left(\frac{-4 \pi G}{3} \left(\rho_U(r) + \frac{3 P_{\text{exp}}(r)}{c_0^2} \right) \right) - \frac{g_{zp}}{R_U} = \frac{3 c_0^2}{2 R_U^2} \implies \ddot{a}(R_U) = 6.921 \cdot 10^{-37} \text{ s}^{-2}.$$

Delivering the first derivative of the Hubble parameter with respect to time at $r = R_U$, i.e. for scale

parameter at $a = 1$ yields: $\dot{H}_0 = \frac{\ddot{a}(R_U)}{a} - H_0^2$ hence: $\dot{H}_0 = -3.924 \cdot 10^{-36} \text{ s}^{-2}$.

6.3. Minimum size of the Universe

Let us assume a hypothetical big bang situation, meaning all energy of the Universe would be located within the smallest possible diameter. The total energy in the current Universe is made up by the gravitational zero-point energy, the rest energy of mass, and radiation & thermal energy, while the latter one is assumed neglectible [11]: $W_{zpU} = M_U \cdot c_0^2$ and $W_{mU} = M_U \cdot c_0^2$. Using the Heisenberg uncertainty relation normalized with Planck-units, for minimum time and minimum diameter it is yielded:

$$\hbar \leq (\alpha \cdot W_{Pl}) \cdot \left(\frac{t_{Pl}}{\alpha} \right) \quad \text{with:} \quad \alpha = \frac{2 \cdot M_U \cdot c_0^2}{W_{Pl}} \quad \text{and} \quad t_{U00} = \frac{t_{Pl}}{\alpha} \implies t_{U00} = 9.872 \cdot 10^{-106} \text{ s}$$

and $d_{U00} = c_0 \cdot t_{U00} = 2.959 \cdot 10^{-97} \text{ m}$.

A change in mass of the Universe over its evolution does not need to be treated explicitly here due to equivalence of mass and energy. However, a condition for energy conservation is, that no mass or energy has crossed the border of the Universe. The analysis of the zero-point distance r_{fluc} for the fluctuation of motion that is caused for a body by uncertainty delivers an alternative path to the

same result: $2 \cdot r_{fluc} = \frac{\hbar}{2 \cdot M_U \cdot c_0} = 2.959 \cdot 10^{-97} \text{ m}$.

As a third path, the same is also resulting from the relativistic gravitational Bohr model, if the groundstate is assumed with only one Ghoton in the Universe filled with the rest energy of the mass of the Universe – see section 2.3.1. .

A forth path to the minimum size is given by the de Broglie relation, indicating the groundstate level

Gravon which is half of the Ghoton energy: $\frac{\lambda_{U00}}{2} = \frac{h}{2 * 2 * \pi * M_U * c_0} = 2.959 \cdot 10^{-97} \text{ m} .$

6.4. Quantum gravitational coupling parameter

To describe the coupling between a body in a gravitation potential and its quantum, a gravitational coupling constant shall be derived analogous to the Sommerfeld fine-structure constant for electrodynamics [28].

The Sommerfeld fine-structure constant¹² α_C is based on the Bohr atom model. It relates the velocity of the electron on its trajectory in a hydrogen atom in groundstate $n = 1$ to the speed of light. Hence it serves for example to describe emission- and absorption rates of photons from the electron. With

the Bohr radius: $r_B = \frac{4 * \pi * \epsilon_0 * \hbar^2}{m_e * q^2}$ the electron velocity is:

$$v_e(1) = \frac{h}{2 * \pi * r_B * m_e} = \frac{q^2}{2 * \epsilon_0 * h} \quad \text{and hence:} \quad \alpha_C = \frac{v_e(1)}{c_0} = 7.292 \cdot 10^{-3}$$

Analogous to the derivation as for the electrodynamic case in the Bohr atom model, a gravitational coupling parameter is obtained. For the gravitational zero-point level it is:

$$- W_{spot} = \frac{m * M_U * G}{R_U} = m * c_0^2 = W_{kin} = W_{zp} . \text{ A relativistic approach is needed here:}$$

$$W_{kinr} = m * \gamma * c_0^2 \quad \text{and} \quad \gamma = 2 \quad \implies \quad v = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} * c_0 = 2.598 \cdot 10^8 \frac{m}{s} .$$

Hence for the zero-point energy level of the Universe at its boarder $r = R_U$ we yield as the minimum

$$\text{gravitational coupling parameter: } \alpha_{Gzp} = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} = 0.866 .$$

The value is about two orders of magnitude larger than that for electrodynamic Coulomb coupling. Within the Universe α_{Gzp} will be running, i.e. increase further towards up to the value of one, if mass body approaches speed of light. Hence strong emission-/absorption interaction of Ghotons with mass bodies in the Universe must be expected.

6.5. Gravitational pressure and inflational acceleration of the Universe

To calculate gravitational pressure the hydrostatic approach is applied:

12 : With subscript C used to denote that this coupling constant is related to Coulomb potential.

$$P_{g_U}(R_U) = \int_0^{R_U} \rho(r)^* g_U(r)^* dr = \int_0^{R_U} \frac{\rho_{U^*} r^3 / R_{U^*}^3 M_{U^*} G}{r^2} dr = \rho_{U^*} g_{mU} = \frac{1}{2} \rho_{U^*} c_0^2 .$$

In this the mean gravitational acceleration is found to be $g_{mU} = \frac{M_{U^*} G}{2 R_U^2} = 1.018 \cdot 10^{-10} \frac{m}{s^2}$, identical to the value of the zero point acceleration g_{zp} derived above.

However, the mean gravitational radial acceleration $g_U(r)$ is always directed towards the observer at $r=0$ and its value depends on the distance to an observed object. Hence this cannot explain violation of galaxy rotation structures with missing acceleration in themselves. Moreover, for different distances observed with constant missing gravitational acceleration a_0 , this can also not be explained with $g_U(r)$. Even more, the violation is also found for galaxies with rotational planes perpendicular to the radial direction of observation, where g_{mU} would not deform perceived galaxy rotation structure.

Other inflation based acceleration parameters – in addition to qualitative mismatch with observations – also quantitatively cannot explain missing gravitational acceleration in galaxy rotation structures. Acceleration would be too low for a typical galaxy:

$$a_{\text{exp}}(r) = H_0^2 r \quad \implies \quad a_{\text{exp}}(R_{Gx}) = 8.715 \cdot 10^{-15} \frac{m}{s^2} \quad \text{with:} \quad R_{Gx} = 1.892 \cdot 10^{21} m .$$

Attributed to the entire Universe, acceleration would be more than an order of magnitude too large:

$$a_{\text{exp}}(R_U) = H_0^2 R_U = 2.037 \cdot 10^{-9} \frac{m}{s^2} .$$

Also with a relativistic approach the value obtained would be too large as compared to observations: $a_{\text{exp}}(R_U) = H_0 v_{\text{inf}} = H_0 c_0 = 6.441 \cdot 10^{-10} \frac{m}{s^2}$.

To summarize, a non-quantum mechanical approach as described in this section cannot explain observed gravitational acceleration.